

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Entrepreneurial potential: An exploratory study of women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs in Uttarakhand

Uma Raikhola ^{1,*} and Vinay Chandra ²

Department of Commerce, M. B. Govt. P.G. College, Haldwani, (Nainital), Uttarakhand, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 1153–1164

Publication history: Received on 14 December 2022; revised on 26 January 2023; accepted on 28 January 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0128>

Abstract

Entrepreneurship plays a significant role for growth and development of the nation. In India, women make up roughly half of the population. However, their contribution to the country's economic progress is smaller than that of men. Women own and operate only 8.05 million of the total 58.5 million enterprises. Entrepreneurial potential may be defined the willingness and propensity of a person to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Individuals' entrepreneurial potential can be evaluated with the aid of their entrepreneurial skills and competences. The present study focuses on identifying the entrepreneurial potential among women both women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs of Uttarakhand. The research is based on descriptive and exploratory research. The data was collected from 550 women respondents including 190 women entrepreneurs and 360 non entrepreneurs. This study is based on primary as well as secondary data. The study found that the entrepreneurial competencies among women entrepreneurs are higher than that of non-entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship; Potential; Willingness and propensity; Entrepreneurial skills and competencies; Women entrepreneur

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship is the process of starting a new business and providing employment opportunities for those who are willing to take on any of risk to earn more profit by producing or distributing goods and services to meet the needs of people. In India, women make up roughly half of the population. However, their contribution to the country's economic progress is smaller than that of men. Women own and operate only 8.05 million of the total 58.5 million enterprises. Only 14% of female entrepreneurs in India are involved in the business. Entrepreneur is derived from the French word 'entreprendre,' which means 'to undertake.' An entrepreneur is a person or company that takes on the responsibility of creating, organising, managing, and risking a business.

Entrepreneurial motives, psychological competence, social competence, and management skills are the primary dimensions that can explain entrepreneurial potential. (Lus Currel et al., 2013). Entrepreneurial potential, in essence, connects a set of psychological, behavioral, and social traits observed in successful entrepreneurs that are thought to be convergent in explaining a representative construct for the conceivable behavior of becoming an entrepreneur (Krueger & Brazeal, 1994). The willingness and propensity of a person to engage in entrepreneurial activities is referred to as entrepreneurial potential. Individuals' entrepreneurial potential can be evaluated with the aid of their entrepreneurial skills and competences. The involvement and participation of women in the process of development is essential for the upliftment of the women and to raise their role and status in the society. To become a successful entrepreneur an individual must have entrepreneurial qualities such as Passion, Motivation, Creativity, Self- Confidence, Vision, Adaptability, Risk Tolerance, Decision making ability, Leadership quality, Ability to network, Problem solving ability, Good communication skills etc.

*Corresponding author: Uma Raikhola

Entrepreneurial potential exists within an individual and distinguishes between an entrepreneur's internal capacities and external resources that are required to conduct entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurial potential is determined by the relationship between the environment and an individual's beliefs, attitudes, and assumptions. The entrepreneurial potential aids in determining one's readiness to start a business. It is a crucial component in the long-term success of entrepreneurship in the economy (Ryan et al. 2011). Entrepreneurial potential is a more fundamental concept than entrepreneurial purpose (Alsos & Kolvereid, 1998; Erikson, 2006).

Entrepreneurship can be used as one of the key factors of economic development by involving women in entrepreneurial activities. More women entrepreneurs increase economic diversity Verheul et al., (2004). Women constitutes almost fifty percent of the world population. The hidden entrepreneurial potential of women has gradually been changing with the growing sensitivity to the role and economic status in the society. The socio-economic participation of women at the international, regional, national and local levels means using significant potential resources more effectively. Women can benefit from available opportunities worldwide by increasing their empowerment. Entrepreneurship occupies an important place in the process of economic development. It has become a key concept in social and human development discourse; it is considered to be a factor of economic and human development Abubakar (2010).

2. Development of Entrepreneurial Potential Model

Individuals' entrepreneurial potential can be evaluated with the aid of their entrepreneurial competencies. The definition of entrepreneurial competencies is the knowledge, abilities, beliefs, attitudes, personalities, and expertise that support entrepreneurial action (Kiggundu, 2002; Morris et al., 2013) and Success (Dixon et al., 2005). The following competences have been used by the researcher to evaluate the entrepreneurial potential of women in Uttarakhand.

- Self-sufficiency/ Freedom,
- Need for achievement/ Success-
- Leadership quality
- Need for Challenges and ambitions
- Creativity / Imagination
- Self-confidence / Enthusiasm
- Tolerance towards ambiguity
- Risk taking ability
- Problem solving capacity
- Action oriented

2.1. Self-sufficiency/ Freedom

Those seeking independence and freedom want to be in charge of their own lives, be able to set their own rules and restrictions, and, in short, be able to make their own decisions.

2.2. Need for achievement/ Success

A continuous desire of excellence, performance enhancement, and innovation is described as the need for achievement. People who have a high need for achievement are more committed to their goals and work harder than those who have a low need for achievement.

2.3. Leadership Quality

People who enjoy having control and power frequently have a strong desire to lead and the ability to influence. Such individuals seek to collect resources and organise actions in specific terms.

2.4. Need for Challenges and ambitions

The need for challenges and ambitions goes hand in hand with the desire to succeed. These people are always looking for ways to take on challenging tasks and realise their goals.

2.5. Creativity / Imagination

Someone who is curious, inquisitive, capable of foreseeing events, and able to come up with different solutions to a problem frequently demonstrates creativity.

2.6. Self-confidence / enthusiasm

Self-confidence is the belief in one's own capabilities and resources. Someone with self-assurance is positive about their potential to succeed and is aware of their own worth.

2.7. Tolerance towards ambiguity

It can be described as a person's comfort level with ambiguity, unpredictability, and divergent viewpoints. A person's capacity to function well in a hazy environment is a sign of their ambiguity tolerance.

2.8. Risk taking ability

Risk-taking is a reflection of one's risk-taking attitude. It has to do with your capacity to face uncertainty and acknowledge that you might lose money, autonomy, or reputation.

2.9. Problem solving capacity

The ability to handle challenging or unforeseen professional scenarios as well as intricate commercial difficulties is referred to as having a problem-solving capacity.

2.10. Action oriented

Action oriented people are those who are prepared or likely to take practical steps to address an issue or set of circumstances.

The researcher adapted the questions for evaluating women's entrepreneurship potential from "Self-assessment, test your entrepreneurial potential.

The model consists of 10 competencies with a total of 28 statements. Self-sufficiency and freedom are assessed using three statements. (Example of an statement: "I prefer being my own boss" The need for achievement and success is assessed by 3 statements (example: I always try to learn from my failures); Leadership quality by three statements (example: I enjoy leading others); Need for Challenges/Ambition assessed by three statements (example: being overly ambitious is frequently perceived negatively); Creativity/Imagination assessed by three statements (example: I am fairly curious and am constantly on the lookout for new discoveries); Self-Confidence/Enthusiasm assessed by two statements (example: when I take on a project, I am confident that I will complete it successfully). Tolerance towards ambiguity is assessed by 3 statements (example: For me, solving a challenging task is more enjoyable than one that is simple); risk-taking ability is assessed by 2 statements (example: For me, taking a risk is like buying a lottery ticket); problem-solving capacity is assessed by 3 statements (example: when faced with difficulties, I look for alternative solutions); and action-oriented is assessed by 3 statements (example: I am not afraid to take an initiative).

These statements are scored on a 5-point Likert scale with the following anchors: 1- Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3- Neutral, 4- Agree, and 5- Strongly Agree. To assess their entrepreneurial potential, respondents were asked to rate each statements on a five-point Likert scale according to how much they agreed or disagreed with it. Pretesting of the scale was done by the researcher to check the validity and reliability of the scale.

3. Review of literature

Mintzberg (1973) the entrepreneurial approach entails a continuous search for new possibilities and growth. Both past strategy- and entrepreneurship-related research have been used to derive the most common entrepreneurial qualities and dimensions. The three traits that were derived are inventiveness, risk-taking, and initiative.

Lumpkin and Dess (1996) add two more in the forms of competitive aggressiveness and autonomy. These elements are meant to complement one another and improve the firm's entrepreneurial performance. These characteristics are independence, creativity, initiative, assertiveness in competition, and risk-taking. These five factors could be used to gauge an individual's or an organization's entrepreneurial orientation.

One of the more widely used tools for measurement is the "Entrepreneurial Potential Questionnaire" by King (1985) which assesses six traits in the form of need for achievement, internal locus of control, problem-solving orientation, propensity for taking risks, and manipulation/assertiveness.

Krueger and Brazeal (1994) suggested that the entrepreneurial potential is prior to the entrepreneurial intentions. In fact, having the potential to be an entrepreneur does not imply that the individual wish to make use of it, or that the environment and context is favorable for it. Thus, an individual can have a high potential to be an entrepreneur, but does not consider launching a venture (that is, does not have an entrepreneurial intention). Researchers share this vision about the relation between entrepreneurial potential and intentions. The former refers to the individual perception about its capacity and the later refers to the wish to engage in entrepreneurship activities.

The level of new business start-ups is generally favorably correlated with perceptions of people's abilities (Arenius and Minniti, 2005; Arin et al., 2015; Dilli et al., 2018).

The entrepreneurial potential, in essence, connects a number of psychological, behavioral, and social traits frequently observed in successful businesspeople and is regarded convergent in the explanation of a representative construct for a probable behaviour: to start a business. (Krueger & Brazeal, 1994; Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000).

D.C. North (2005) Potential for entrepreneurship as perceived by non-entrepreneurs who believe they possess the abilities required to pursue entrepreneurship.

According to Santos' (2008) theory, the definition of a potential entrepreneur is a construct supported by three dimensions of successful entrepreneur traits—Achievement, Planning, and Power—and a fourth complimentary dimension of desired traits—Entrepreneurial Intention. Each dimension has elements that have been identified as entrepreneurial qualities. The following characteristics are found in the achievement dimension: opportunity recognition, perseverance, and efficiency. Goal-setting, information-searching, continuous planning, and permanent control are all characteristics of the planning dimension. Persuasiveness and the ability to create a network of relationships are two characteristics that fall under the power dimension. Furthermore, there is a desire to launch a firm in the dimension of entrepreneurial intention.

Susana Correia Santosa *, Antonio Caetanoa and Luis Curreal (2013) in their study "Psychosocial aspects of entrepreneurial potential" presented a theoretical model for the concept of entrepreneurial potential as well as the key psychosocial factors that influence an individual's capacity to engage in activities typically associated with entrepreneurship. Their study's overarching research question was: How can the entrepreneurial potential construct be theoretically explained and experimentally evaluated? An instrument (the EPAI - Entrepreneurial Potential Assessment Inventory) was developed by the study's researchers to assess the entrepreneurial potential construct. Four studies on its empirical validation were offered by the researchers in their study. According to the findings, the scale has valid convergent and discriminate properties. An entrepreneur can utilize the EPAI for self-evaluation, training, and career development.

The management competencies, psychological competencies, social competencies, and entrepreneurial motivations are the four primary elements of the entrepreneurial potential Assessment Inventory model. There are 11 sub dimensions altogether inside these four primary dimensions.

4. Research methodology

4.1. Objectives of the study

- To explore the entrepreneurial potential of women (entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs) in Uttarakhand.

4.2. Hypothesis

- H₀: There is no significant difference in entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.
- H₁: There is a significant difference in entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

4.3. Research Design

This research is based on descriptive and exploratory in nature.

4.4. Sampling procedure

For the study purpose three districts (Bageshwar, Alomra and Nainital) from Kumaun region and three districts (Dehradun, Haridwar and Chamoli) from Garhwal region of Uttarakhand have been selected.

4.4.1. Sampling Techniques

A sample approach called "multistage cluster sampling" has been utilized. Districts were picked in the first stage through lottery method of random sampling. The second stage involved picking blocks from selected districts. From each district two blocks have been selected by the researcher. Village selection took place at the third stage. From each block 4 villages have been selected by the researcher. Same process (lottery method) was followed in selecting block from each district and selecting villages from each blocks) In the fourth stage, women respondents, both entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, were selected through purposive sampling and snow ball sampling.

4.4.2. Sample size

The population of the study is not defined. The Sample size came out to be 385 at 5% significance level by using Cochran formula.

Researcher filled 600 questionnaires from the respondents which were more than 385 as calculated. Survey was conducted in six district of Uttarakhand hence researcher choose a sample size more than 385 assuming that some of these questionnaires would be rejected due to incomplete or wrong information. Out of 600, 395 women respondents were those who were not engage in entrepreneurial activity and 205 respondents were women entrepreneurs. 100 samples were collected from each district giving equal representation to each block. 50 samples were taken from each block giving equal representation to each village. The responses of 50 respondents got rejected due to problem with incorrect or missing information, making them unfit for the purpose of analysis. Researcher found 550 questionnaires which were relevant for the study. That was much more than the minimum level of sample size that was required. Researcher has used the data of 550 respondents to gain considerably more clarity on the topic. Out of 550 respondents, 360 were women respondents and 190 were women entrepreneurs.

The bifurcation of area wise data is as shown in Table 1

Table 1 Area wise data collection

S.N.	District Sample	Block Sample	Villages	Non entrepreneurs	Women Entrepreneures
1.	Almora (92)	Chaukhutiya (46)	Masi	7	6
			Bakhali bisht	7	3
			Dhudaliya Bisht	7	5
			Ganai	8	3
				29	17
		Dwarahat(46)	Bhatora	9	2
			Basera	8	3
			Dharam gaon	8	4
			Malli Mirai	7	5
				32	14
2.	Bageshwar (89)	Kapkote (44)	Chaura	8	3
			Gadera	8	2
			Sama	6	6

			Nakuri	8	3
				30	14
		Bageshwar (45)	Dhapoli	8	3
			Kanda	9	3
			Are	7	4
			Bohala	8	3
				32	13
3.	Nainital(96)	Bhimtal(47)	Chafi	8	3
			Saungoan	9	4
			Jeolikote	7	4
			Ranibag	7	5
				31	16
		Haldwani(49)	Malli Bamori	6	7
			Bhagwanpur	8	5
			Bithoria	8	4
			Lamachaur	8	3
				30	19
4.	Dehradun (96)	Raipur (49)	Aamwala	7	6
			Ladpur	8	4
			Motharowala	6	6
			Harrawala	8	4
				29	20
		Vikasnagar (47)	Ambari	7	5
			Dhakrani	9	3
			Badam wala	6	6
			Babugarh	7	4
				29	18
5.	Haridwar (91)	Roorkee (45)	Barampur	6	5
			Dharampur	7	4
			Bhoori	8	3
			Imlikhera darampur	6	6
				27	18
		Bhagwanpur(46)	Sirchandi	7	5
			Khedi Shikohpur	6	4
			Sisona	7	6
			Sikkanderpur Bhainswal	7	4

				27	19
6.	Chamoli (86)	Dasoli (43)	Dewar khadora	8	3
			Bachher	8	2
			Chhinka	9	2
			Gauhana	8	2
				34	9
		Gairsain (43)	Ganwali	7	2
			Panchali	8	3
			Rohira	8	3
			Gair	7	5
				30	13
		Total	360	190	

4.4.3. Sources of Data

The present study is based on both primary as well as secondary data.

Primary data

Primary data were collected by the researcher herself through structured questionnaire.

Secondary data

Secondary data has been gathered from a variety of journals, books, periodicals, thesis, dissertation, Annual report of MSMEs and newspapers. Important data was also gathered from a variety of websites.

Table 2 Reliability of assessment of entrepreneurial potential among Women

Cronbach alpha value	N (items)
0.901046	28

In order to ensure the reliability of questions related to assessment of entrepreneurial potential researcher calculated cronbach's alpha. The values of alpha was computed and presented in table shows that the alpha value is more than 0.7, the value of alpha is 0.90 which means, it is acceptable for the study.

4.4.4. Pilot Study

The questionnaire so developed was pretested. The researcher in the current study conducted a pilot study on a small sample of 30 female respondents and 20 women entrepreneurs in order to check the reliability, feasibility and validity of the and make sure it was within acceptable bounds. So the researcher would continue with the questionnaire's final administration.

5. Analysis and Interpretation

Entrepreneurial potential scale consists of ten competencies with a total of 28 statements. A 5-point Likert scale was used to evaluate the entrepreneurial competencies, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree," 2 "disagree," 3 "neutral," 4 "agree," and 5 "strongly agree." Self-sufficiency/ Freedom

5.1 Tests of Normality

A crucial decision-making process for selecting central tendency measurements and statistical methodologies for data analysis is the test of normality. Parametric tests are used to compare the groups when the data have a normal

distribution; otherwise, nonparametric tests are used. To find Normality of test, Kolmogorov- Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk test is employed in SPSS. Table 4.73 shows the results of the normalcy test.

Table 2 Tests of Normality

	Employment_ status	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Self-sufficiency / Freedom	Non Entrepreneur	0.174	360	<0.001	0.946	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.166	190	<0.001	0.947	190	<0.001
Need for achievement / Success	Non Entrepreneur	0.163	360	<0.001	0.926	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.185	190	<0.001	0.935	190	<0.001
Leadership Quality	Non Entrepreneur	0.137	360	<0.001	0.939	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.157	190	<0.001	0.942	190	<0.001
Need for Challenges / ambitions	Non Entrepreneur	0.178	360	<0.001	0.943	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.236	190	<0.001	0.898	190	<0.001
Creativity / imagination	Non Entrepreneur	0.133	360	<0.001	0.949	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.168	190	<0.001	0.937	190	<0.001
Self-confidence / Enthusiasm	Non Entrepreneur	0.195	360	<0.001	0.911	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.238	190	<0.001	0.911	190	<0.001
Tolerance towards ambiguity	Non Entrepreneur	0.212	360	<0.001	0.843	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.232	190	<0.001	0.853	190	<0.001
Risk taking ability	Non Entrepreneur	0.196	360	<0.001	0.917	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.219	190	<0.001	0.924	190	<0.001
Problem solving capacity	Non Entrepreneur	0.132	360	<0.001	0.962	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.147	190	<0.001	0.943	190	<0.001
Action oriented	Non Entrepreneur	0.177	360	<0.001	0.949	360	<0.001
	Entrepreneur	0.186	190	<0.001	0.929	190	<0.001

Data is not normally distributed, as shown by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test result. The data is considered normal if the p value is larger than 0.05, but in this situation, the sig. value is less than 0.05. It denotes a considerable departure from the normal distribution of the data. Hence nonparametric test (Mann whitney U test) has been used to entrepreneurial competencies of women non entrepreneurs and women entrepreneurs.

To examine whether or not entrepreneurial competencies differ between two independent groups (women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs), the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test has been used. The Mann-Whitney U test has been applied on the total score of each variable. A significance level of 0.05 has been applied.

5.2. Mann-Whitney U Test

Table 3 Mean rank of entrepreneurial competencies between Women Entrepreneurs and Non Women Entrepreneurs

Ranks				
Entrepreneurial Competencies	Employment_status	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Self-sufficiency / Freedom	Entrepreneur	360	323.00	80751.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	235.91	70774.00
	Total	550		
Need for achievement / Success	Entrepreneur	360	306.64	74866.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	249.55	76659.00
	Total	550		
Leadership Quality	Entrepreneur	360	292.92	73230.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	260.98	78295.00
	Total	550		
Need for Challenges / ambitions	Entrepreneur	360	299.12	74781.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	255.81	76744.00
	Total	550		
Creativity / imagination	Entrepreneur	360	308.57	77142.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	247.94	74382.00
	Total	550		
Self-confidence / Enthusiasm	Entrepreneur	360	307.72	76930.50
	Non Entrepreneur	190	248.65	74594.50
	Total	550		
Tolerance towards ambiguity	Entrepreneur	360	294.72	7679.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	259.49	77846.00
	Total	550		
Risk taking ability	Entrepreneur	360	287.58	71894.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	265.44	79631.00
	Total	550		
Problem solving capacity	Entrepreneur	360	304.92	76229.00
	Non Entrepreneur	190	250.99	75296.00
	Total	550		
Action oriented	Entrepreneur	360	298.26	74267.50
	Non Entrepreneur	190	255.69	76707.50
	Total	550		

5.2.1. Self-sufficiency/ Freedom

The data in Table 4.74 reveals that the mean rank of self-sufficiency or freedom for women entrepreneurs is 323.00, whereas it is 235.91 for non-women entrepreneurs. According to the data, entrepreneurs have a mean rank that is

greater than non-entrepreneurs. Between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, there is a significant gap in the mean rank of self-sufficiency/freedom.

5.2.2. Need for achievement / Success

In terms of the need for achievement or success, entrepreneurs have a higher mean rank than non-entrepreneurs. The mean rank of women entrepreneurs and women non-entrepreneurs is 306.64 and 249.55, respectively. There is a significant difference in the mean rank of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs regarding the need for achievement and success.

5.2.3. Leadership Quality

The mean rank of entrepreneurs is greater than that of non-entrepreneurs in terms of leadership qualities. The mean rank for women entrepreneurs and women non-entrepreneurs is 292.92 and 260.98, respectively. In terms of leadership quality, there is a little difference in the mean rank of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs

5.2.4. Need for Challenges / ambitions

The mean rank of Need for challenges / ambitions in case of women entrepreneurs is 299.12 and women non-entrepreneurs is 255.81. The data indicates that the mean rank of women entrepreneurs is significantly higher than the mean rank of women non-entrepreneurs.

5.2.5. Creativity / imagination

Entrepreneurs score 308.57 on the creativity/imagination scale, whereas non-entrepreneurs score 247.94. According to the data, the mean rank of women entrepreneurs is noticeably greater than the mean rank of women non-entrepreneurs. The mean rank of creativity and imagination differs significantly between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

5.2.6. Self-confidence / Enthusiasm

The mean rank of self-confidence and enthusiasm for women entrepreneurs is 307.72, whereas it is 248.65 for non-entrepreneurs. According to the data, the mean rank of entrepreneurs is noticeably greater than the mean rank of women non-entrepreneurs. The mean rank of self-confidence and enthusiasm differs significantly between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

5.2.7. Tolerance towards ambiguity

In case of tolerance towards ambiguity the mean rank of women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs is 294.72, 259.49 respectively. There is a slight difference in the mean rank of tolerance towards ambiguity between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

5.2.8. Risk taking ability

The mean rank of Risk taking ability in case of entrepreneurs is 287.58 and non-entrepreneurs are 265.44. The mean rank of entrepreneurs is much higher than the mean rank of non-entrepreneurs. Between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, there is a slight variation in the mean rank of risk-taking ability.

5.2.9. Problem solving capacity

Entrepreneurs rank on average higher than non-entrepreneurs when it comes to problem-solving ability. Entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs mean rank 304.92 and 250.99 in terms of their ability to solve problems, respectively.

5.2.10. Action oriented

The mean rank for women entrepreneurs is 298.26, while it is 255.69 for non-entrepreneurs. In comparison to non-entrepreneurs, entrepreneurs have a mean rank that is much higher. The mean rank of action orientation differs slightly between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

From the table 2, it is found that there is the greatest difference between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs in terms of self-sufficiency and freedom, while the smallest difference is discovered in terms of risk-taking abilities.

Table 4 Mann Whitney U test on Entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-women entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurial Competencies	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Self-sufficiency / Freedom	25624.000	70774.000	-6.513	<0.001
Need for achievement / Success	29716.000	73866.000	-4.285	<0.001
Leadership quality	33145.000	78295.000	-2.398	0.017
Need for Challenges / ambitions	31594.000	76744.000	-3.231	0.001
Creativity / imagination	29233.000	74383.000	-4.542	<0.001
Self-confidence / Enthusiasm	29444.500	74594.500	-4.520	<0.001
Tolerance towards ambiguity	32696.000	77846.000	-2.647	0.008
Risk taking ability	34481.000	79631.000	-1.751	0.080
Problem solving capacity	30146.000	75296.000	-4.044	<0.001
Action oriented	31557.500	76707.500	-3.198	0.001

Mann-Whitney U test results presented in Table 4.75. It shows statistically significant difference in entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs in all variables (Self sufficiency / Freedom: $z = -6.513$, $p < 0.001$, Need for achievement / Success: $z = -4.285$, $p < 0.05$, Leadership quality: $z = -2.398$, $p < 0.05$, Need for Challenges / ambitions: $z = -3.231$, $p < 0.05$, Creativity / imagination: $z = -4.542$, $p < 0.05$, Self confidence / Enthusiasm: $z = -4.520$, $p < 0.05$, Tolerance towards ambiguity: $z = -2.647$, $p < 0.05$, Problem solving capacity: $z = -4.044$, $p < 0.05$, Action oriented: $z = -3.198$, $p < 0.05$) except Risk taking ability. Therefore, at a 5% level of significance, there is a significant difference in entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. So the null hypothesis is rejected. The null hypothesis is accepted only in the case risk taking ability because the p-values (0.080) are greater than the significance level (0.05).

6. Results and discussion

From the data we found that women entrepreneurs have higher entrepreneurial skills than non-entrepreneurs and highest difference regarding entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs was found in case of self-sufficiency and freedom and lowest in case of risk taking abilities.

Limitation of the Study

- The study is restricted to just 12 blocks across six districts in Uttarakhand. As a result, the study's findings cannot be applied generally.
- The study results only relied on the responses provided by the sample, there may be a possibility that some respondents may have been biased.
- The sample size is small; the results can only be regarded as indicative one. The study only included 550 women, so the sample size may not fully reflect Uttarakhand female population.

Suggestions

- The women of Uttarakhand have enormous entrepreneurial potential, so the government should encourage women towards entrepreneurial activities by providing beneficiary schemes for them as well as creating awareness among them regarding these schemes.
- Government should conduct seminars, workshops and training for the women to develop their skills and knowledge and provide information regarding how to utilize their skills in entrepreneurial activities so that they can start their own business and contribute to the economic development of the state.
- The most crucial aspect in women's empowerment is education. Therefore the literacy programmes should be properly implemented by the government to enhance the standard of education among women in India.

- Vocational training and Technical education should be provided to the women entrepreneur

7. Conclusion

Entrepreneurial potential is defined as the non-entrepreneurs who perceive that they have necessary skills to engage in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial potential is a set of attitudes, motives, skills and capabilities to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurial potential, in essence, connects a set of psychological, behavioural, and social traits observed in successful entrepreneurs that are thought to be convergent in explaining a representative construct for the conceivable behaviour of becoming an entrepreneur (Krueger & Brazeal, 1994). Women represent more or less half of the world's population. In India, women make up roughly half of the population. However, their contribution to the country's economic progress is smaller than that of men. Women of Uttarakhand have immense potential. The study conclude that women respondents both entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs of Uttarakhand have entrepreneurial skills to become a successful entrepreneurs. From the data we found that women entrepreneurs have higher entrepreneurial skills than non-entrepreneurs and highest difference regarding entrepreneurial competencies between women entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs was found in case of self-sufficiency and freedom and lowest in case of risk taking abilities. The lack of financial assets in the majority of women's names, except jewellery, makes it difficult for them to take risks out of fear of losing money, which limits their ability to take risks as both entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. The government should provide financial and marketing assistance to women so that they can start their own businesses.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

A formal acknowledgement will hardly meet the ends of justice in the expression of my deep sense of gratitude and obligation to all those who helped me in the completion of this research work. This research is the result of guidance, help and inspiration of several people throughout the study.

My deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Vinay Chandra, Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, M.B.G.P.G. College, Haldwani, Nainital, Uttarakhand, for his valuable suggestions, inspiring guidance and all out support in writing this research , from the conceptual to completion stage. Without his guidance and persistent help this research would have not been possible.

I am very much thankful to my respondents for their co-operation in completing my research work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

We have no conflict of interest during this research.

Statement of informed consent

I am aware that my confidentiality as a participant in this study will be protected and that the researcher will not use my name in any reports based on the information gathered from this survey. Records and data shall be used in the future only in accordance with established data use regulations that safeguard both institutions' and individuals' privacy.

References

- [1] Agrawal Rinku (2018). Role of Entrepreneurship in Promoting Women Empowerment in North Eastern Region of India. Amity Journal of Entrepreneurship, Vol. 3, Issue 2, pp. 25-41.
- [2] All India Report of Sixth Economic Census. <http://msme.gov.in>
- [3] Annual Report of MSME 2020-21
- [4] Bhowmik S.R. & Bhowmik M. (2007). Entrepreneurship: A tool for economic Growth and A Key to Business Success (1st Ed.). Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- [5] Brush, C. (1992). Research of Women Business Owners: Past trends, a new Perspective, Future Directions, Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice, 16: 5-30.

- [6] B.Ramesh (2018). Problems and Prospective of Women Entrepreneurship. International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR) , Volume 5, Issue 1 , www.ijrar.org (E-ISSN 2348-1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138).
- [7] Chaturvedi Rao P. (2021). Women Entrepreneur: The Key for Unlocking India’s True Potential. Retrieved from www.businessworld.in
- [8] Donald F. Kuratko. (2014). Introduction to Entrepreneurship. International Edition (9th ed.). Canada: Ohlinger Publishing Service. pp. 4.
- [9] Goyal Meenu and Jai Parkash (2011). Women Entrepreneurship in India: Problems and Prospects. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, Vol.1 , Issue 5, September 2011, ISSN 2231 5780
- [10] International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, Vol.1 , Issue 5, September 2011, ISSN 2231 5780.
- [11] Kumar N. (2021). Status of Women Entrepreneur in Indian Start-up. International Journal of Engineering technology and Management Science Vol. 5, Issue 2, March 2021, ISSN: 2581-4621.
- [12] Mahajan Shikha (2013). Women Entrepreneurship in India. Global Journal of Management and Business Studies, Volume 3(10), 1143-1148.
- [13] Prakash, Goyal (2011) . Women Entrepreneurship in India: Problem and Prospects. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, Vol.1 (5).
- [14] Lenka Usha and Agarwal Sucheta. (2017). Role of women entrepreneurs and NGOs in promoting entrepreneurship: case studies from Uttarakhand, India. Journal of Asia Business Studies, Vol. 11 (4), 451-465.
- [15] Krueger N.F, Brazeal D.V.(1994). Entrepreneurial Potential and Potential entrepreneurs. *Entrepren. Theory Pract.*, 18 (3), pp. 91-104. Retrieved from <https://www.rresearchgate.net>
- [16] Mintzberg, H. (1973). *The Nature of Managerial Work*. New York: Harper and Row.
- [17] Lumpkin, G.T. & Dess, G.G. (1996). Clarifying the entrepreneurial orientation construct and linking it to performance. *Academy of Management*.21, pp. 135-172
- [18] kumar Vijaya and jayachitra (2013). Women Entrepreneurs in India: Emerging issues and challenges. *International Journal of Development Research*, Vol. 3 (4), pp. 012-017.
- [19] Santos, P. C. F. (2008). *Uma escala para identificar potencial empreendedor (tese de doutorado)*. Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis.
- [20] Santosa Susana Correia, Caetanoa Antonio and Curreal Luis. (2013). Psychosocial aspects of Entrepreneurial Potential. *Journal of small business & Entrepreneurship*, 26(6), pp. 661-685. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>
- [21] Kaimal S Devapriya, Thomas Allan and. Amritha V. S. (2020). Entrepreneurial Potential of Apipreneurs in South Kerala. *Journal of Extension Education*, Vol. 32(2), pp. 6515-6519. Retrieved from <https://extensioneducation.org>
- [22] Kumari Pallawi.(2017).Unfolding Potential of Women Entrepreneurs for enhancing Economic Empowerment and Efficiency. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, Vol.05 (8), 126-133. Retrieved from <https://www.indianjournals.com>
- [23] Sinha Poonam. (2016). Problems and Prospects of Women Entrepreneurship in Uttarakhand. *Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, Volume 18(5 or ver. II) 89-95. Retrieved from www.iosrjournals.org.
- [24] V. Jyothi and Prasad G.(1993).A Profile of Potential Rural Women Entrepreneurs. *SEDME*, Vol. XX (1), 23-37. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com>
- [25] Rani C. (1986).Potential Women Entrepreneurs– A Study. *SEDME*, 13(3), 13-32. <https://journal.sagepub.com>
- [26] Singh, N.P. and Gupta, Rita Sen. (1990).Potential Women Entrepreneurs - Their Profile, Vision and Motivation. Research report, Serial 1, National Institute of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development, New Delhi
- [27] Self-assessment, test your entrepreneurial potential. Retrieved from <https://www.bdc.ca>